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Deal exclusivity in cross-cultural e-commerce

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper was to investigate the effect of deal exclusivity on accommodation booking intention, with regard to both hedonic and utilitarian aspect of the offer. Also, the role of cultural background was examined to see whether the consumers from different cultures response to deal exclusivity differently. In an experimental survey, a total of 208 persons participated (113 persons from the Netherlands and 95 persons from Vietnam). They judged an online advertisement of a room accommodation (an exclusive offer for members only vs. an inclusive offer for everyone). The findings showed that deal exclusivity did not directly influence consumers' booking intention. An indirect effect emerged through deal evaluation. The relationship between perceived exclusivity and the intention to book the service was influenced by the utilitarian evaluation, i.e., the exclusive offer was evaluated as more useful than the inclusive offer. In addition, a more positive utilitarian evaluation implied a higher booking intention. In contrast, no indirect effect via the hedonic evaluation of the offer was evidenced. Culture did not moderate the strength of the effect. However, this study found supporting evidence for the effect of culture on consumer's booking intention. Specifically, Dutch consumers expressed much higher booking intention than Vietnamese consumers, regardless of the exclusivity of the deal. Moreover, the more indulgent the consumers were, the more likely they would book the room accommodation.

Keywords: E-commerce, consumer behaviour, cross-cultural, exclusivity

1. Introduction

The digitalization of marketplaces is a golden opportunity for businesses to expand their current customer base beyond the border of a nation. At the same time, this adds more challenges to the already brutal battlefield of international marketing, since businesses need to appeal to consumers coming from different cultural backgrounds. As e-commerce affords consumers to explore a much larger pool of options than before, the task of persuading them to purchase from a certain (web) shop instead of others becomes more gruelling than ever. Marketers turn to price promotion as a way to attract new customers and to retain existing ones. While seasonal sales or inclusive, open-for-all offers are still the most common forms of price promotion, exclusive and targeted deals available to only a selected group of consumers are rising in popularity (Barone & Roy, 2010) [3, 4]. Consumers nowadays can easily search for other deals, other sources of supply, compare the offers of different web shops, or even find an alternative for the product (Martinez & Kim, 2012) [8]. Therefore, the exclusive experience that marketers want to create might be at stake. When options are plenty, it is unsure if deal exclusivity alone can influence the purchase intention. In addition, Orji (2016) [20] and Broeder and Derksen (2018) [5-7] found that the effect of deal exclusivity might not be universal. Consumers from different cultures might respond differently towards deal exclusivity; some might prefer it more than the others. Hence, the present study examines the influence of deal exclusivity on consumers' preferences online. A comparison is made of consumers from two different cultures: the Netherlands and Vietnam.

2. Literature review and hypothesis development

2.1. Scarcity and membership

Deal exclusivity is often linked with the notion of scarcity. Cialdini and Goldstein (2002) anticipate that consumers tend to yearn for items or opportunities that are extremely difficult for the masses to obtain. The ownership of something rare and low in supply triggers the sense of uniqueness, which is a quality sought after by many (Eisend, 2008) [10]. Scarcity appears in various forms. The effectiveness of scarcity is empirically supported in the case of limited quantity (Aggarwal, Jun, & Huh 2011; Jang *et al.*, 2015) [1] and limited edition

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(Shin, Eastman, & Mothersbaugh, 2017) [25]. In a traditional retail setting (Gierl, Plantsch, & Schweider, 2008) [11], scarcity is claimed to be effective in boosting the perceived desirability of the product as well as positively affecting consumer behaviour. However, whether this effect remains the same in the online space is still questionable (Jeong & Kwon, 2012; Lee *et al.*, 2015; Broeder & Derksen, 2018) [5-7]. When choosing the target group for the exclusive offer, oftentimes marketers turn to the consumers in their membership program first. This kind of program is a way to maintain relationships with high value shoppers, as well as to reward customers for their loyalty with the brands (Martinez & Kim, 2012) [8]. Membership gives consumers many advantages over non-membership. The most obvious ones are the monetary benefits. Many businesses provide discounts, gifts or extra services for their loyal club members. Members of the membership program are also the first to know about the latest updates and deals. Many brands, especially high-end ones, offer special experiences to their private club members. This membership-only availability exudes the feeling of exclusivity and uniqueness, since it is not something that an average consumer can access (Martinez & Kim, 2012) [8]. In other words, membership is sometimes used as a status symbol, an expression of one's belongingness to an elite group. Not all memberships are meaningful to its members. People generally tend to value membership of a small but close-knit group with distinct characteristics rather than of a large but loosely connected group (Barone & Roy, 2010b) [3, 4]. The higher amount of efforts and resources consumers invest into achieving their membership status, the more they see themselves as the member of the deal recipient group, and the more they associate themselves with the characteristics of that group (Barone & Roy, 2010b) [3, 4]. Membership enhances consumers' commitment and customer loyalty. The more a deal recipient identifies as a member of the deal target group, the stronger the effect of deal exclusivity. In addition, a (scarce) exclusive offer is more favourable to an inclusive offer (Barone & Roy 2010a) [3, 4]. Hence, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 1: An exclusive offer has a more positive behavioural effect on consumers than an inclusive offer.

2.2. Deal evaluation

Before making any purchase, consumers take both utilitarian and hedonic evaluation of the offer into consideration. Utilitarian value (what a product does) is assessed in terms of product functionality and practical benefits such as value for money, convenience, efficiency of shopping procedure, etc.; while hedonic value is judged by the experiential benefits that the product or service can offer (Anderson *et al.*, 2014) [2]. Usually, hedonic values (what a product makes people feel) involve enjoyment, entertainment, pleasures and many other positive emotions. Many studies show that utilitarianism and hedonism are not two sides of the same spectrum, but two separate and closely connected dimensions in consumers' decision-making process (Chiou & Ting, 2011; Anderson *et al.*, 2014; Richard & Habibi, 2016) [2, 8, 22]. Hence, exclusive, members-only offers allow consumers to buy the product with a better price than usual (utilitarian), and at the same time give them the impression of uniqueness (hedonic). Depending on the context in which shopping takes place,

utilitarian and hedonic evaluations can impact consumers mindset and behaviours in varying degree. In the context of online shopping, the importance of the hedonic evaluation might be outgrowing that of the utilitarian one. Scarpi (2012) [23] noted that hedonism is more profitable, since it influences the amount of purchases and re-visiting intentions of online customers. Contrarily, Anderson *et al.* (2014) [2] postulated that online experiential shopping is effective in inducing only loyalty but not purchase intention. Exclusivity can play an important role in accelerating the hedonic value of the product or the opportunity, as seen in the success of many luxury brands. Barone and Roy (2010b) [3, 4] propose that self-enhancement mediates the effect of deal exclusivity and deal recipient evaluation. If the deal recipients see the offer as a chance for them to enhance their sense of self, they will show a more favourable evaluation towards the deal. The following hypothesis is formulated:

Hypothesis 2: The hedonic and utilitarian deal evaluation will influence the effect of offer exclusivity on the behavioural intention of consumers.

2.3. Cultural differentiations

Culture, to some extent, governs people's mindset and behaviours; and buying behaviours are no exception. Orji (2016) [20] found that people from individualistic cultures are more susceptible to scarcity than collectivistic ones, because they perceive personal uniqueness to be more important than group value. However, Broeder and Derksen (2018) [5-7] find a contradictory result in their study. Western consumers from a highly individualistic country (the Netherlands), appreciated inclusive offers more; whereas Mexican consumers, who are more collectivistic, were more prone to exclusive offers. In addition to individualism, another cultural difference that is closely linked to exclusivity and hedonism is indulgence (Hofstede, 2020) [13, 14]. It is defined as the extent to which people try to regulate their impulsive wants. People coming from an indulgence-oriented culture are expected to put less effort in controlling of their desires, while placing great importance on their wellbeing and gratifications. They are highly optimistic, and optimistic consumers tend to spend more and make more discretionary purchases. On the contrary, people from restrained cultures impose a high level of control on their personal desires, and focus on social goals instead of their own emotions (Sharma, Sivakumaran, & Marshall, 2011) [24]. Therefore, consumers from restrained countries like Vietnam and China usually think very carefully before making any purchase (Broeder & Snijder, 2018; Broeder & Wildeman, 2020) [5-7]. They are less likely to make impulse purchases than the individualist, indulgent consumers in the Western countries. Consumers from indulgent cultures feel less guilty about consuming products merely for hedonic purposes, because they can reason their buying decision as a way for them to enhance their sense of self and make themselves happy. At the same time, the utilitarian benefits of a promotion deal also provide motivation and justification for them. Thus, they are more likely to spend money than consumers from restrained cultures (Pandey & Devasagayam, 2015) [21]. For that reason, the current study will explore the moderating role of cultural background on the relationship between deal exclusivity and behavioural intention:

Hypothesis 3: The effect of deal exclusivity and deal evaluation on behavioural intention will be influenced by culture (differentiated by individualism and indulgence)

The individualistic and indulgent culture of this study is set to be from a Western-European country, the Netherlands. On the other end, Vietnam is the chosen restraint culture of this study. Vietnam has a collectivistic culture that is high on prudence and low in indulgence (Sharma, Sivakumaran,

& Marshall, 2011; Broeder & Wildeman, 2020; Hofstede, 2020) [5-7, 13, 14].

3. Materials and Method

The present study had a two (exclusivity offer: inclusive, exclusive) by two (culture: Dutch, Vietnamese) between-subjects design. The conceptual model is given in Figure 1.

Fig 1: Conceptual model of the present study

Deal evaluation (hedonic and utilitarian) was the mediator. Culture was expected to influence the relationship between offer type and booking intention. Participants were randomly assigned to one of two conditions with a different offer.

3.1. Sample

Originally, a total of 271 persons completed an online survey. Their cultural background was identified through self-identification (“To what ethnic group do you belong?”), which had to match with the birth-country and the country-of-living (“the Netherlands” or “Vietnam”). Mismatches (*N* = 69) in this cultural identification were omitted. The final sample consisted of 208 persons. There were 113 Dutch persons living and born in the Netherlands (mean age: 24 years; age range: 18-54 years), and 95 Vietnamese persons living and born in Vietnam (mean age: 24 years; age range: 18-36 years). According to Hofstede (2020) [13, 14] Vietnam has a high uncertainty avoidance national culture (score 30 on a 0-100 scale). The Netherlands has a lower avoiding uncertainty score, 53. This indicates that Vietnamese consumers preferably avoid ambiguous or uncertain (buying) situations, compared to Dutch consumers. This is confirmed by Broeder & Wildeman’s (2020) [5-7] study, in which both cultural groups are defined through self-identification.

3.2. Advertisement

The participants were presented with an advertisement for an accommodation offer. There were two variations: an exclusive variation, “offer for members only!” (See Figure 2), and an inclusive variation, “offer for everyone!” (See Figure 3).

Fig 3: Accommodation presented in an advertisement as an inclusive offer

The composition of the advertisements was based on the original Airbnb way of displaying. Some elements were deleted for their potential confounding effect: i.e., the price per night, the rating, and the location (in both the search field and the description of the accommodation). All elements indicating an Airbnb environment were also deleted to avoid that the respondents were influenced by the reputation of Airbnb.

3.3. Questionnaire

The participants were asked to imagine the following scenario: “you are looking for an accommodation for a short trip”. Then they were shown the advertisement with the accommodation offer and were asked some questions.

- Booking intention was measured with one statement (“I would like to book this accommodation”). Answers were given on a 5-point-scale (“strongly (dis)agree”).
- The hedonic deal evaluation scale consisted of four adjective pairs related to experiential quality (“How do you feel about this promotion offer? ... (not) enjoyable, frustrating/relaxing, (no) fun, boring/exciting”).
- The utilitarian deal evaluation scale consisted of four adjective pairs related to the practical benefits of the offer (“How do you feel about this promotion offer? ... pointless/useful, (not) informative, stupid/ sensible, (not) beneficial”).

In order to capture cultural differences, the levels of prudence, indulgence, and uncertainty avoidance were measured.

- The prudence scale had four statements adapted from

Fig 2: Accommodation presented in an advertisement as an exclusive offer

Sharma, Sivakumaran, and Marshall (2011) [24] (e.g., “I am a cautious shopper”), and a 5-point-scale (“strongly (dis)agree”).

- The indulgence scale had four statements adapted from Sharma, Sivakumaran, and Marshall (2011) [24] (e.g., “I buy things for pleasure”), and a 5-point-scale (“strongly (dis)agree”).
- Uncertainty avoidance was measured with seven items adapted from Jung and Kellaris (2004) [16] (e.g., “I prefer structured situations to unstructured situations”), and a 5-point-scale (“strongly (dis)agree”).

The following scales checked whether the inclusive/exclusive manipulation in the experiment was successful.

- The exclusivity scale consisted of four adjective pairs (“This offer is ... available to very few/many customers, (not) exclusive, (no) selective, (not) restricted”).
- The targeting scale has two adjective pairs (“This offer is ... (not) targeted at me, standardized/selected for me”).

For some scales, the internal consistency was checked with Cronbach’s α : for hedonic evaluation $\alpha = .80$, for utilitarian evaluation $\alpha = .77$, for prudence $\alpha = .76$, for indulgence $\alpha = .67$, and for uncertainty avoidance $\alpha = .81$, for exclusivity $\alpha = .73$ (in exclusive condition) and $\alpha = .85$ (in inclusive condition). Scales have a good reliability with Cronbach’s α higher than .70.

4. Results

4.1. Manipulation check

Table 1 shows the results for the manipulation check questions. Two independent-samples t-tests were conducted to compare the perceived exclusivity and targeting in both conditions. On average, the exclusive offer was perceived as more exclusive than the inclusive offer, $t(206) = 14.80, p = .003, d = 2.06$. The exclusive offer was also perceived as more targeted than the inclusive offer, $t(206) = 2.04, p = .001, d = .28$. So, the intended experimental manipulation to present two different type of offers was confirmed.

Table 1: Manipulation check: means on a 5-point-scale, 1 = min. and 5 = max., with standard deviations

	Exclusive condition (N = 101)	Inclusive condition (N = 107)
Exclusive perception	3.73 (0.82)	1.86 (0.98)
Targeted perception	2.45 (0.96)	2.14 (1.21)

Table 2 shows the cultural differences between the two groups in the sample of this study. On average, the Dutch participants were more indulgent than the Vietnamese participants, ($t(206) = 4.420, p < .001, d = .52$). In addition, the

Vietnamese participants scored higher on prudence, $t(206) = -3.461, p = .001, d = .50$ and uncertainty avoidance, $t(206) = -3.978, p < .001, d = .58$. This cultural comparison implied that the assumed differences between the Dutch and Vietnamese groups were confirmed.

Table 2: Cultural differences between the Dutch and Vietnamese samples: means on a 5-point-scale, 1 = min and 5 = max., with standard deviations

	Dutch (N = 113)	Vietnamese (N = 95)
Indulgence	3.94 (0.54)	3.66 (0.54)
Prudence	3.18 (0.68)	3.50 (0.61)
Uncertainty avoidance	3.11 (0.76)	3.47 (0.43)

4.2. The effect of exclusivity on booking intention

An ANOVA showed no significant interaction between exclusivity and culture ($F(1, 208) = 0.32, p = .570$). There was a significant main effect of culture, $F(1, 208) = 26.81, p < .001$, partial eta squared = .11. The Dutch participants reported a higher booking intention ($M = 4.02, SD = 0.68$) than the Vietnamese respondents ($M = 3.39, SD = 1.06$). No significant main effect of exclusivity was found, $F(1, 208) = 0.739, p = .391$. Hypothesis 1 was not supported. The relationship between the exclusive offer versus the inclusive offer and purchase intention for the Dutch and Vietnamese participants is visualized in Figure 4.

Fig 4: Relationship between exclusive/inclusive offer and booking intention per culture.

4.3. The effect of deal evaluation

To examine whether booking intention can be explained by the deal evaluation, a regression analysis was performed using PROCESS procedures developed by Hayes (2018) [12]. In the parallel multiple mediator model, the variable offer type was the predictor. The two mediators were hedonic evaluation and utilitarian evaluation. The outcomes of this regression are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Regression coefficients, standard errors (SE) and model summary information (based on 5000 bootstrap samples) for the influence of the exclusive/inclusive offer parallel multiple mediator model depicted in Figure 5

		Dependent										
		M_1 (Hedonic)			M_2 (Utilitarian)				Y (Booking intention)			
Independent		Coeff.	SE	p		Coeff.	SE	p		Coeff.	SE	p
X (Offer)	a_1	-0.101	0.107	.345	a_2	-0.264	0.106	.013*	c'	0.184	0.124	.198
M_1 (Hedon.)		---	---	---		---	---	---	b_1	0.006	0.111	.958
M_2 (Util.)		---	---	---		---	---	---	b_2	0.420	0.112	< .001*
Constant	iM_1	3.121	0.171	< .001	iM_2	3.593	0.169	< .001	iy	2.092	0.352	< .001
		$R^2 = 0.004$			$R^2 = 0.029$				$R^2 = 0.122$			
		$F(1,206) = 0.895, p = .345$			$F(1,206) = 6.185, p = .013^*$				$F(3,204) = 9.514, p < .001^*$			

In the regression analyses bias corrected and accelerated (BCa) confidence intervals (CI) were based on 5000 bootstrap samples. The confidence intervals should be entirely above or below zero. Also, in this analysis there was no evidence that the type of offer directly influenced booking intention ($c' = 0.184$, 95% BCa CI [-0.06, 0.43]). However, the bootstrap confidence interval revealed the indirect effect of the utilitarian evaluation ($a_2b_2 = -0.11$), 95% BCa CI [-0.24., 0.02]). The exclusive offer was evaluated as more useful than the inclusive offer ($a_2 = -0.264$, 95% BCa CI [-0.48, -0.05]). In addition, the utilitarian evaluation was found to positively contribute to booking intention ($b_2 = 0.420$, 95% BCa CI [0.20, 0.64]). For the hedonic evaluation no indirect effect on booking intention was found ($a_1b_1 = 0.006$, 95% BCa CI [-0.03, 0.03]). This partly supported Hypothesis 2.

Fig 5: A statistical diagram of the parallel multiple mediator model for the presumed influence of exclusivity

4.4. The effect of culture

The assumption was made (Hypothesis 3) that culture influenced the effect of offer type. Two simple moderation analyses were performed with Hayes’ (2018) [12] procedures (model 1). Culture was entered as independent variable and offer type was the moderator. The utilitarian evaluation and the hedonic evaluation were dependent variables. The outcomes of the analyses of the regression are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Regression coefficients, standard errors (SE) and model summary information (based on 5000 bootstrap samples) for the influence of the inclusive/exclusive offer on the utilitarian evaluation and the hedonic evaluation

Independent	Dependent							
	Y1 (Utilitarian)			Y2 (Hedonic)				
	Coeff.	SE	p	Coeff.	SE	p		
X (Culture)	d_1	-0.288	0.105	.006*	e_1	0.088	0.108	.417
W (Offer)	d_2	-0.251	0.104	.017*	e_2	-0.105	0.107	.330
W x X	d_3	0.201	0.210	.338	e_3	0.121	0.216	.574
Constant		3.191	0.052	<.001		2.963	0.054	<.001
	$R^2 = 0.067$			$R^2 = 0.009$				
	$F(3,204) = 4.941,$ $p = .002^*$			$F(3,204) = 0.625,$ $p = .596$				

Firstly, cultural differences had a main effect on the utilitarian evaluation ($d_1 = -0.288$, 95% BCa CI [-0.49, -0.08]). The Dutch group evaluated the exclusive offer as more useful compared to the Vietnamese group. There was also a significant main effect for offer type ($d_2 = -0.251$, 95% BCa CI [-0.46, -0.04]). The exclusive offer was evaluated as more useful than the inclusive offer. No interaction effect between culture and offer type was found (d_3).

Secondly, cultural differences had no main effect on the

hedonic evaluation of the offer ($e_1 = -0.088$, 95% BCa CI [-0.49, -0.19]). There was no significant main for offer type and the hedonic evaluation ($e_2 = -0.105$, 95% BCa CI [-0.44, -0.14]). Also, no interaction between culture and offer type was found. (e_3). This partly supported Hypothesis 3. The relationships between the inclusive/exclusive offers and the deal evaluation per cultural group are visualized in Figure 6 (for the utilitarian evaluation) and in Figure 6 (for the hedonic evaluation).

Fig 6: Relationship between the offer type and the utilitarian evaluation per culture

Fig 7: Relationship between the offer type and the hedonic evaluation per culture

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Scarcity is believed to exude the sense of uniqueness, and therefore, enhancing the perceived value and desirability of a product or an opportunity (Eisend, 2018; Shin, Eastman, & Mothersbaugh, 2017) [10]. By using various forms of scarcity, including deal exclusivity, marketers hope to increase sales, as well as to create a one-of-a-kind experience for their customers. Previous studies by Barone and Roy (2010a, 2010b) [3, 4] discover that exclusive deals elicit more positive attitude than inclusive ones. At the same time, meaningful membership in a loyal customer program is believed to strengthen the feeling of exclusivity and uniqueness. These positive qualities are expected to result in more positive behavioural intentions online.

The findings of the present study partly supported the initial expectations. Firstly, deal exclusivity of the offer, specifically membership-only availability, did not directly affect booking intention. Secondly, when the hedonic and

utilitarian evaluation of the offer were added into the model as mediators, an indirect effect emerged. The relationship between perceived exclusivity and participants' intention to book the service was influenced by the utilitarian evaluation, i.e., the exclusive offer was evaluated as more useful than the inclusive offer. In addition, a more positive utilitarian evaluation implied a higher booking intention. In contrast, no indirect effect via the hedonic evaluation of the offer was evidenced. Thirdly, in this study cultural differences between the Dutch and Vietnamese groups were confirmed. The Dutch participants, who were highly indulgence-oriented compared to the Vietnamese participants, showed a much higher intention to book the accommodation, regardless of the exclusivity of the offer they received. However, the assumption that cultural differences would influence the effect of deal exclusivity on behavioural intention was not supported by the data.

6. Limitations and further research

While this research contributes to the existing knowledge on cross-cultural persuasion as well as online consumer behaviours, certain limitations might hinder the generalizability of the findings.

The first limitation is that the questionnaire was created and distributed solely in English. Of course, all participants needed at least average English proficiency to complete the questionnaire. Still, there is a possibility that some participants did not understand the statements fully and consequently chose the answers that were slightly different from their true evaluations. Future research, if not limited in time, should attempt to provide a precise, reliable translation for the non-English speaking participants to ensure the most accurate responses from them.

A second limitation might be that in the present study the perceived targeting of the accommodation offer was low. This should be addressed in future research. Perceived targeting is closely linked to personalization, and personalization can be an important factor in the relationship between deal exclusivity and consumers' behaviours. In this study, the participants might not feel that the exclusive offer was targeting at them or tailored for them. The failure to manipulate the sense of targeting might have weakened the effect of exclusivity and membership. It is sensible to argue that the more consumers see that the deals are created specifically for them, the more they appreciate it and the higher chance of them purchasing the presented product. Therefore, future research should find ways to improve the sense of targeting, in order to explore the effect of targeted, exclusive deal on purchase intention.

Finally, the demographic profile of the Vietnam might affect the generalizability of this study. Vietnamese participants are generally young, mostly millennials. Right now, they are the largest group of consumers in the country, with high consumption power and a changing consumption habit (Cho *et al.*, 2014; Nguyen *et al.*, 2016)^[9]. They are educated, living in urban areas. In fact, a large percentage of the Vietnamese participants in our study were living in Ho Chi Minh City, the metropolis of Vietnam. Other demographic groups like rural and sub-urban consumers, or older age groups were underrepresented in the sample. There are grounded reasons to suspect that certain gaps exist between different demographic and socio-economic groups. The young Vietnamese consumers who were born after the post-war reform grew up in a time of economic boom and

impressive increase in household income. With more money at their disposal and a modern lifestyle, their indulgence level might deviate from that of the previous generations who suffered poverty and trade ban. At the same time, consumers in the big cities, for the most part, have much higher income and also higher living standards than those from the countryside. Therefore, their hedonic consumption mindset is expected to differ from those in rural areas. Due to the aforementioned reasons, the findings of this study can be used to predict the response of young urban consumers in Vietnam, but when applying for the larger population, they should be taken with caution. While the indulgence orientation of Vietnamese consumers is expected to have risen drastically due to economic growth, it is still well below the indulgence level of Dutch consumers. Therefore, when communicating the benefits of the promotions to Vietnamese consumers, it is recommended that the marketers focus on the practicality of the deals. As for the Dutch, the marketers should emphasize the enjoyment and gratification aspect.

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